

Determination of Aflatoxin B1 and Total Aflatoxin (B1, B2, G1, and G2) Risk in Pistachios and Dried Figs Collected from Local Markets in Şanlıurfa by High Performance Liquid Chromatography Method

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Abstract

Aflatoxins are mycotoxins produced by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* molds and have carcinogenic, mutagenic, and teratogenic effects. These toxins, which are especially common in dried foods such as nuts, corn, peanuts, pistachios, figs, and spices, pose a serious threat to human health and food safety. Aflatoxins, which are a major risk factor for public health, agriculture and international trade on a global scale, occur especially under inappropriate harvesting, storage, and processing conditions. This problem, which is seen in export products such as pistachios and figs in Türkiye, causes economic losses and obstacles in international trade. Precautions to be taken before and after harvest, storage of products separately and providing appropriate conditions are of great importance for the prevention of aflatoxins. The aim of this study was to determine the aflatoxin risk in pistachios and figs. Aflatoxins were detected in 16 samples of dried pistachios and 5 samples of dried figs taken from the open market in Şanlıurfa and some of the samples exceeded the accepted limit values. While G1 and G2 were detected in 3 of the pistachio samples, AFB1 was detected between 0.21-404.62 ppb in 4 samples and AFB2 was detected between 0.1-0.96 ppb in 3 samples. Total aflatoxin content ranged from a minimum of 5.04 ppb to a maximum of 405.58 ppb with an average of 108.53 ppb. In addition, when the aflatoxin contents of dried fig samples were analyzed, the presence of AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2 was detected in some samples. Aflatoxin AFG1 (0.03 ppb) and AFG2 (0.05-0.06 ppb) were detected in 1 fig sample and AFB1 and AFB2 were detected in 3 fig samples. AFB1 was detected between 25.16-44.45 ppb in 3 samples and AFB2 was detected between 0.01-6.07 ppb in 3 samples. Total aflatoxin content ranged from a minimum of 0.56 ppb to a maximum of 51.15 ppb with an average of 25.105 ppb. In this study, aflatoxin was found in some of the pistachio and fig samples. Aflatoxin formation may increase due to unfavorable conditions especially in drying and storage processes. Therefore, careful management and strict control of the drying and storage stages is of great importance to reduce the risk of aflatoxins. Such measures play a critical role in both ensuring food safety and maintaining product quality.

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1. Introduction

Aflatoxins are secondary metabolites produced by molds of the species *Aspergillus parasiticus* and *Aspergillus flavus* and are considered among the most significant types of mycotoxins (Fernane et al., 2010). These harmful substances can cause both acute and chronic poisoning due to their mutagenic, carcinogenic, and teratogenic effects (Marin et al., 2013). Aflatoxins are a common issue in dried foods such as nuts, corn, peanuts, pistachios, figs, and spices (Blankson and Mill-Robertson, 2016). Mold contamination is a significant risk factor in dried products, posing a major threat to human health and food safety, in addition to causing economic losses. Dried fruits are particularly vulnerable to mold growth and toxin accumulation due to their sensitivity to cultivation conditions, processing methods, and storage environments (Peter and Cotty, 2017). On a global scale, mycotoxins are regarded as a serious risk to public health, agriculture, international trade, and the economy (Özer et al., 2012; Özer et al., 2017b). Fungal infections lead to the loss of approximately 10% of global crops annually (Zhang et al., 2012). However, only a portion of this loss is attributed to mycotoxins. Among mycotoxins, aflatoxins are of particular concern due to their high toxicity potential and widespread prevalence, representing a significant global health issue (Özer et al., 2012; Özer et al., 2017a). The most common mycotoxins include aflatoxin (AF), ochratoxin, trichothecenes, zearalenone, patulin, cyclopiazonic acid, and fumonisin (Kumar et al., 2008; O'Riordan and Wilkinson, 2008). To prevent the formation of aflatoxins in food products, necessary measures must be taken starting from the harvest stage (Özer et al., 2024). The mycotoxin problem persists widely in products sold in local markets and for export, particularly in pistachios and figs. The most significant issue in pistachio exports is the rejection of products at customs due to non-compliance with the importing country's regulations. This situation leads to substantial financial losses and penalties, negatively impacting export activities (Aslan, 2017). Aflatoxins can contaminate pistachios during

pre-harvest, harvest, processing, and storage stages (Ji et al., 2022). Dried figs are produced by drying the mature fruits of *Ficus carica domestica* L. trees either mechanically or under the sun in open air. Figs are one of Türkiye's economically significant export products, cultivated in the Mediterranean coastal region and Central Anatolia (Akova, 2009). Due to their high sugar content and the conditions during harvest and post-harvest processes, figs are prone to mold and mycotoxin formation (Karbancıoğlu and Heperkan, 2008). Molds typically thrive at 25 °C and 80% relative humidity (Cemeroğlu and Özkan, 2004). One of the primary reasons for the aflatoxin problem in pistachios in Türkiye is the practice of farmers storing their products under uncontrolled conditions after drying. Changing this long-standing habit will take time. However, it is estimated that certain methods applied during the harvest period could significantly reduce aflatoxin formation in pistachios. Pistachio fruits that are damaged for any reason are more likely to develop mold, which can lead to aflatoxin production. Similarly, pistachios that fall to the ground after ripening, known as "ground pistachios," are more exposed to harmful molds in the soil, increasing the risk of mycotoxin formation. Therefore, it is believed that taking necessary precautions in the orchard before harvest, separating damaged fruits post-harvest, and storing ground pistachios separately from normal fruits could significantly reduce the risk of mycotoxin formation (Tekin and Şahan, 2014). Research has shown that pre-harvest aflatoxin production is caused by climatic stresses such as drought, high temperatures, and rainfall, as well as insect damage and unsuitable climatic conditions for the plant's genotype (Wu and Khlangwiset, 2010). Post-harvest toxin contamination, on the other hand, can occur due to improper agricultural practices during storage, transportation, and food processing (Özer et al., 2024). Among aflatoxins, aflatoxin B1 is known to have the highest toxic effect (Gürhayta and Çağındı, 2015). Aflatoxins (B1, B2, G1, and G2) have been found to exhibit acute toxic effects in experimental animals. However, aflatoxins are

primarily notable for their carcinogenic properties. Aflatoxin B1 has been identified as a cause of liver cancer in experimental animals. Regular consumption of aflatoxin-contaminated foods can lead to liver tumors in humans, and studies on animals have shown that aflatoxins can cause birth defects and genetic mutations (Betna, 1989). According to the Turkish Food Codex Contaminants Regulation (TGK, 2011) and European Union food legislation (EU, No 165/2010), the maximum allowable limit for aflatoxin B1 is 5 ppb, and for total aflatoxins, it is 10 ppb (Anonymous, 2010). However, since aflatoxin limits vary by country, they complicate international trade (Özer et al., 2017b). This study aims to investigate the presence of aflatoxins, which are carcinogenic, toxic to the liver, and cause genetic mutations, in pistachios and figs. Samples of pistachios and figs were collected from open markets in

Şanlıurfa, located in the Southeastern Anatolia Region of Türkiye. Aflatoxin levels were measured in both pistachio and fig samples. The results indicate that aflatoxins were detected in these products and that contamination can occur during drying, storage, and transportation processes. Therefore, this study focuses on examining four aflatoxin types B1, B2, G1, and G2 which have carcinogenic potential in pistachios and figs.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental materials and tools

In this study, 16 samples of dried pistachios and figs were randomly sampled from spice shops in open markets in Şanlıurfa province in the Southeastern Anatolia Region of Türkiye. For each sample, 50 grams of product was used in this study (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A sample from the sampling points of pistachio and fig samples sold in the open market and a view of the extraction stage

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Aflatoxin analysis

Aflatoxin analysis was performed using the HPLC system according to AOAC Official Method 999.07 (Anonymous, 2000). There are three main steps in this analysis: extraction, cleaning, and injection into HPLC.

2.2.2. Preparation of samples for analysis and methods used

Dried pistachio and fig samples collected from open markets were brought to the laboratory in 100-gram transparent plastic bags, and 50 grams of each sample were used for analysis. The detection of aflatoxins in pistachio and fig samples was carried out

through extraction, HPLC conditions, and aflatoxin quantification. For pistachio extraction, 4 grams of NaCl, 100 ml of distilled water, and 150 ml of methanol were added to 50 grams of the sample. The mixture was shaken (GFL 3006 Model shaking device) at high speed for 3 minutes and filtered through filter paper. From the filtrate, 5 ml was taken and mixed with 5 ml of PBS solution. For fig extraction, 5 grams of NaCl, 60 ml of distilled water, and 240 ml of methanol were added to 50 grams of the sample. The mixture was shaken at high speed for 3 minutes and filtered through filter paper. From the filtrate, 6 ml was taken and mixed with 60 ml of PBS solution. These extracts were then passed through an

immunoaffinity column and sent to the HPLC device for reading. The HPLC-FLD device used in the analysis was a SHIMADZU Nexera XR 20 series, which operates at a wavelength range of 365-435 nm. For aflatoxin analysis, Tables 1 and 2 specify the sampling points of the dried pistachio and fig products and the types of aflatoxins examined. Finally, the

samples were sent to the HPLC-FLD for analysis to determine aflatoxin levels. Each sample was analyzed in duplicate. Additionally, Figure 2 illustrates the steps followed for quantifying aflatoxin B1, B2, G1, and G2, and Table 3 presents the maximum aflatoxin levels in pistachios and figs in our country.

Table 1. Points where pistachio samples were collected for aflatoxin analysis and aflatoxin species analyzed

Sample No	Sample Name	Where chili pepper samples were taken	Aflatoxin Analyzed
1	Urfa- Pistachio 1	Spice market, workplace number 1	B1, B2, G1, G2
2	Urfa- Pistachio 2	Spice market, workplace number 2	B1, B2, G1, G2
3	Siirt- Pistachio 3	Spice market, workplace number 3	B1, B2, G1, G2
4	Urfa- Pistachio 4	Spice market, workplace number 4	B1, B2, G1, G2
5	Urfa- Pistachio 5	Spice market, workplace number 5	B1, B2, G1, G2
6	Siirt- Pistachio 6	Spice market, workplace number 6	B1, B2, G1, G2
7	Urfa- Pistachio 7	Spice market, workplace number 7	B1, B2, G1, G2
8	Urfa- Pistachio 8	Spice market, workplace number 8	B1, B2, G1, G2
9	Siirt- Pistachio 9	Spice market, workplace number 9	B1, B2, G1, G2
10	Urfa- Pistachio 10	Spice market, workplace number 10	B1, B2, G1, G2
11	Urfa- Pistachio 11	Spice market, workplace number 11	B1, B2, G1, G2
12	Siirt- Pistachio 12	Spice market, workplace number 12	B1, B2, G1, G2
13	Urfa- Pistachio 13	Spice market, workplace number 13	B1, B2, G1, G2
14	Urfa- Pistachio 14	Spice market, workplace number 14	B1, B2, G1, G2
15	Urfa- Pistachio 15	Spice market, workplace number 15	B1, B2, G1, G2
16	Urfa- Pistachio 16	Spice market, workplace number 16	B1, B2, G1, G2

Table 2. Collection points of dried fig samples for aflatoxin analysis and aflatoxin species analyzed

Sample No	Sample Name	Where chili pepper samples were taken	Aflatoxin Analyzed
1	Yellow- Fig 1	Spice market, workplace number 1	B1, B2, G1, G2
2	Yellow- Fig 2	Spice market, workplace number 2	B1, B2, G1, G2
3	Black- Fig 3	Spice market, workplace number 3	B1, B2, G1, G2
4	Yellow- Fig 4	Spice market, workplace number 4	B1, B2, G1, G2
5	Black- Fig 5	Spice market, workplace number 5	B1, B2, G1, G2

Figure 2. Steps for quantification of aflatoxin B1, B2, G1, and G2 species

Table 3. Maximum aflatoxin levels in pistachios and figs in Türkiye (Anonymous, 2011).

	Gıda	Maksimum Limit ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) ppb	
		B1	B1+B2+G1+G2
1	Aflatoksin Pistachios ¹ (directly for human consumption or used as a food ingredient)	8.0	10.0
2	Pistachios ¹ (to be subjected to sorting or other physical processing before being put directly into human consumption or used as a food ingredient)	12.0	15.0
3	Dried fruits: Figs ² (for direct human consumption or used as a food ingredient)	8.0	10.0

3. Results and Discussion

The aflatoxin contents detected in pistachios are presented in Table 4. Upon examining the contents of pistachio samples collected from Şanlıurfa in the Southeastern Anatolia Region, AFB1 was detected in 4 samples, while AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2 were detected in 3 samples. It was determined that 14 of the samples did not contain aflatoxins. Among the 16 pistachio samples obtained from the spice market, AFG1 and AFG2 were detected in 3 samples. AFB2 was detected in 3 of the analyzed samples, with levels ranging between 0.1-0.11, 0.15-0.16, and 0.96 ppb. The AFB1 content in the pistachio samples was found to range from 0.21 to 404.62 ppb. The total aflatoxin content in the pistachios was determined to be at least 5.04 ppb, at most 404.58 ppb, and on average 108.53 ppb. For pistachios intended for direct consumption, the upper limits for aflatoxins are set at $8.0 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (ppb) for AFB1 and 10.0 ppb for total aflatoxins (AFB1 + AFB2 + AFG1 + AFG2) (Anonymous, 2011). As shown in Table 4, aflatoxins were detected in 4 out of 16 dried fig samples. Among the samples with detected aflatoxins, 2 exceeded the threshold limits. The total aflatoxin levels in the Siirt-Pistachio 12 and Urfa-Pistachio 13 samples were measured to be in the ranges of 405.33-405.58 ppb and 15.61-16.19 ppb, respectively. The AFB1 value in the Siirt-Pistachio 12 sample was found to be in the range of 404.37-404.62 ppb, exceeding the threshold limit. Aflatoxin formation in pistachios can occur during harvesting, drying, and storage processes, which may lead to increased aflatoxin levels. Georgiadou et al. (2012), in their study on aflatoxin formation in pistachios,

demonstrated that aflatoxin formation occurs at all stages, including on the tree, during harvest, and in storage. The aflatoxin levels were ranked as $\text{AFB1} > \text{AFG1} > \text{AFB2} > \text{AFG2}$. It was noted that aflatoxin formation occurs during the fruit ripening period but increases during harvest, and levels are higher in orchards damaged by insects. Fernane et al. (2010), in their analysis of 50 pistachio samples collected from the market in Barcelona, Spain, identified mold species such as *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus nigri*, *Aspergillus ochraceus*, and *Penicillium verrucosum*, which have the potential to produce aflatoxins B1 and B2. The analysis revealed that 5 samples exceeded the maximum limits for aflatoxin B1. Sedefoğlu (2013), in their study investigating the presence of aflatoxins in pistachios obtained from the market, detected aflatoxins in 66% of 73 samples, with 2 exceeding the Turkish Food Codex threshold limits. Raad et al. (2014), in their study on mycotoxin exposure in foods (such as nuts, dried fruits, olives, and dates) consumed by individuals in urban areas of Lebanon, found that aflatoxin B1 levels ranged between 0.180 and 0.260 ppb. According to the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) data, which includes European Union countries, 903 food products exported from Türkiye to EU countries between 2011 and 2017 were recalled from the market or rejected at the border due to exceeding mycotoxin limits.

Of these products, 218 were pistachios or pistachio-containing products. After figs (484), pistachios were the most common product to exceed the threshold limits. In the past year, 28 pistachio and pistachio-

containing food products exported from Türkiye to EU countries were found to contain aflatoxins exceeding the established limits (RASFF, 2022).

Table 4. Detected aflatoxin amounts of pistachio

Sample No	Sample Name	AFB1(ppb)	AFB2(ppb)	AFG1(ppb)	AFG2(ppb)	Total AFs (ppb)
1	Urfa-Pistachio 1	-	-	-	-	-
2	Urfa-Pistachio 2	-	-	-	-	-
3	Siirt-Pistachio 3	-	-	-	-	-
4	Urfa-Pistachio 4	-	-	-	-	-
5	Urfa-Pistachio 5-1	4.87	0.11	1.98	0.68	7.64
6	Urfa-Pistachio 5-2	4.81	0.1	1.96	0.68	7.55
7	Siirt-Pistachio 6	-	-	-	-	-
8	Urfa-Pistachio 7	-	-	-	-	-
9	Urfa-Pistachio 8	-	-	-	-	-
10	Siirt-Pistachio 9	-	-	-	-	-
11	Urfa-Pistachio 10	-	-	-	-	-
12	Urfa-Pistachio 11-1	0.69	0.15	3.71	0.78	5.33
13	Urfa-Pistachio 11-2	0.65	0.16	3.43	0.8	5.04
14	Siirt-Pistachio 12-1	404.62	0.96	-	-	405.58
15	Siirt-Pistachio 12-2	404.37	0.96	-	-	405.33
16	Urfa-Pistachio 13-1	0.21	-	11.38	4.02	15.61
17	Urfa-Pistachio 13-2	0.22	-	11.83	4.14	16.19
18	Urfa-Pistachio 14	-	-	-	-	-
19	Urfa-Pistachio 15	-	-	-	-	-
20	Urfa-Pistachio 16	-	-	-	-	-
	Minimum	0.21	0.1	1.96	0.68	5.04
	Maximum	404.62	0.96	11.83	4.14	405.58
	Average	102.56	0.41	5.72	1.85	108.53

-: not detected

The aflatoxin contents detected in fig samples are presented in Table 5. It was determined that 2 of the samples did not contain aflatoxins. Among the 5 fig samples obtained from the spice market, AFG1 and AFG2 were detected in 1 sample. AFB2 was detected in 3 of the analyzed samples, with levels ranging between 6.07-6.7, 0.01, and 0.16-0.19 ppb. The AFB1 content in the fig samples was found to range from 0.47 to 44.45 ppb. The total aflatoxin content in the figs was determined to be at least 0.56 ppb, at most 51.15 ppb, and on average 25.105 ppb. According to the legal standards established by the "Regulation on Maximum Limits for Contaminants in Foodstuffs (2011/28157),"

the permissible upper limits for dried figs are set at 5 µg kg⁻¹ for AFB1 and 10 µg kg⁻¹ for total aflatoxins (B1 + B2 + G1 + G2). As shown in Table 5, aflatoxins were detected in 3 out of 5 dried fig samples. Among the samples with detected aflatoxins, 2 exceeded the threshold limits. The total aflatoxin levels in the Black-Fig 3 and Black-Fig 5 samples were measured to be in the ranges of 46.2-51.15 ppb and 26.82-25.32 ppb, respectively. Similarly, the AFB1 values in the same samples were found to be in the ranges of 40.13-44.45 ppb and 25.16-26.63 ppb, respectively. These AFB1 values also exceeded the threshold limits.

Figure 3. Graph of detected aflatoxin content of pistachio

These measured values surpass the permissible limits and pose a risk to human health with long-term consumption. Total aflatoxins were detected in 11 out of 25 dried fig samples. The total aflatoxin concentrations ranged between 10.10 and 19.81 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. AFB1 was detected in 9 out of 25 dried fig samples, with concentrations ranging from 6.52 to 12.56 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. AFG1 was found in 6 samples, with total AFG1 concentrations ranging from 5.12 to 5.87 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The values of the samples with detected aflatoxins exceeded the legal limits established by the "Regulation on Maximum Limits for Contaminants in Foodstuffs (2011/28157)" (Hepsağ & Hayoğlu, 2022). Kabak (2016), in their study, detected aflatoxins in 16 out of 130 fig samples. Aflatoxin concentrations ranged from 0.1 to 28.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. While all four aflatoxin types were detected, AFB1 was the most prevalent, ranging from 0.1 to 12.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, while AFB2 was found at levels ranging from 0.2 to 10.72 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. AFG1 was detected in three samples, and AFG2 was found in only one sample. According to the analytical results, AFB1 levels exceeded 20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in six dried fig samples. Bircan et al. (2008), using

the HPLC method, analyzed the presence of aflatoxins in a total of 4917 dried fig samples exported from Türkiye to the EU. Total aflatoxin levels were detected in 32% of the dried fig samples, ranging from 10 to 260 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. In a similar study, total aflatoxin contamination was detected in 47.5% of 219 dried fig samples sold in the domestic market and in 23.6% of 2461 dried fig samples intended for export, with values ranging from 10 to 278 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (Bircan ve Koç, 2012). Mimoune et al. (2018), using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) supported by post-column fluorescence detection, analyzed the presence of aflatoxin B1 (AFB1), B2 (AFB2), G1 (AFG1), and G2 (AFG2) in 112 samples of figs, peanuts, and almonds collected from Algeria. The analytical results showed detectable aflatoxin levels in 28 peanut, 16 almond, and 26 dried fig samples. In 69 samples, the total AFB1 levels reached up to a maximum of 174 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. AFB2 was found in 12 samples, ranging from 0.18 to 193 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. In 7 samples, aflatoxin concentrations were detected at low levels. Eleven peanut and 14 dried fig samples exceeded the maximum limits for AFB1 set by the European Union.

Table 5. Detected aflatoxin amounts of fig

Sample No	Sample Name	AFB1(ppb)	AFB2(ppb)	AFG1(ppb)	AFG2(ppb)	TOTAL AFs (ppb)
1	Yellow-Fig 1	-	-	-	-	-
2	Yellow-Fig 2	-	-	-	-	-
3	Black-Fig 3-1	40.13	6.07	-	-	46.2
4	Black-Fig 3-2	44.45	6.7	-	-	51.15
5	Yellow-Fig 4-1	0.48	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.58
6	Yellow-Fig 4-2	0.47	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.56
7	Black-Fig 5-1	26.63	0.19	-	-	26.82
8	Black-Fig 5-2	25.16	0.16	-	-	25.32
	Minimum	0.47	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.56
	Maximum	44.45	6.7	0.03	0.05	51.15
	Average	22.88	2.19	0.03	0.055	25.105

∴ not detected

Figure 4. Graph of detected aflatoxin content of fig

In general, the presence of aflatoxins was detected in pistachio and fig samples. While some samples exceeded the established threshold limits, others remained below these limits. However, samples close to the threshold limits have the potential for aflatoxin levels to increase under suitable conditions. According to the Turkish Food Codex Contaminants Regulation (TGK, 2011) and European Union Food Legislation (EU, No 165/2010), the permissible upper limit for Aflatoxin B1 is set at 5 ppb, and for total aflatoxins, it is 10 ppb (Anonymous, 2010). Among the pistachio and fig samples, there are instances where AFB1

and total aflatoxin levels exceed these threshold limits. Aflatoxin contamination is a global food safety issue that negatively impacts both the marketability and consumption safety of multiple food products (Amaike and Keller, 2011). In addition to compromising food safety, aflatoxin contamination also leads to significant losses in food products. A substantial portion of losses due to aflatoxins affects market value rather than human or animal health. The economic losses caused by aflatoxin contamination are estimated to amount to hundreds of millions of dollars worldwide,

with corn and peanuts being among the most affected products (Mitchell et al., 2016). Furthermore, climate change is predicted to significantly increase the exposure of food products to mycotoxigenic molds and the mycotoxins they produce, threatening the safety of global staple food products (Medina

et al., 2014). Environmental factors linked to climate change, such as drought, high temperatures, and oxidative stress, can further exacerbate aflatoxin contamination in food products (Tian et al., 2021). Figure 5 presents chromatogram graphs showing the aflatoxin peaks of some samples.

Figure 5. Chromatogram plots showing aflatoxin peaks of some samples (a. Blak-fig 3-1, b. Siirt pistachio 12-1)

4. Conclusion

The results of this study reveal the presence of aflatoxins in fig and pistachio samples. In the analysis of fig samples, aflatoxins were detected in 3 out of 5 samples, with AFB1 and

AFB2 found in 2 samples and AFG1 and AFG2 in 1 sample. AFB1 values ranged between 0.47 and 44.45 ppb, while the total aflatoxin levels were measured in the range of 0.56 to 51.15 ppb. Two of the fig samples exceeded the legal limits established by the

"Regulation on Maximum Limits for Contaminants in Foodstuffs (2011/28157)" (5 µg kg⁻¹ for AFB1 and 10 µg kg⁻¹ for total aflatoxins). This was particularly evident in the Black-Fig 3 and Black-Fig 5 samples. Among the pistachio samples, aflatoxins were detected in 4 out of 16 samples. AFB1 values ranged between 0.21 and 404.62 ppb, while the total aflatoxin levels were measured in the range of 5.04 to 405.58 ppb. The Siirt-Pistachio 12 sample significantly exceeded the legal limits for AFB1 (8 µg kg⁻¹) and total aflatoxins (10 µg kg⁻¹). These findings indicate that unsuitable conditions during drying, storage, and harvesting processes contribute to increased aflatoxin formation. Long-term consumption of products containing aflatoxins poses serious risks to human health. Therefore, it is crucial to carefully manage post-harvest processes, ensure proper storage and drying conditions, and conduct regular inspections to minimize aflatoxin risk. These measures will play a critical role in ensuring food safety and reducing barriers in international trade.

Author Contribution Statement

Authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Conflict of Interest Statement

All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest regarding this article.

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